

Effective Use of Cloud Resources: Key to Success of Enterprise Digital Transformation

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Abstract: *The study focuses on how the effective use of cloud resources could be the secret to digital transformation(DT) success. The digital transformation for businesses is a crucial approach critical in improving efficiency in operations and promoting how well the business can grow. There are, however, significant challenges that impact the digital transformation success. The report identifies some of these challenges and the way cloud resources could be used as tools in addressing these concerns. The study findings, therefore, conclude that the effective use of cloud resources is a secret tool crucial to digital transformation success. The TAM model helps to guide the entire report and the analysis method implemented. The results also showcase key recommendations to business leaders and how they can effectively promote digital transformation.*

Keywords: Cloud, DT, ERM, Enterprise goal, TAM model, Leadership, Risk Adverse Culture

Introduction

Businesses all over the world are embracing cloud technology for corporate growth and innovation. This is an entry point for innovative goal-setting and effective business growth (Dash, 2020a). Cloud resources are becoming a popular solution for most businesses today. The rise and growth of e-commerce have contributed to the development of cloud resources. More companies are providing cloud platforms and services to businesses (Jiang et al., 2013). The reliance on cloud resources has been identified as an effective approach to promoting business growth and transformation. It has especially been identified to contribute towards digital transformation success. The cloud is, therefore, a critical tool in promoting and enabling digital transformation.

Given that more and more firms are being urged to embrace a cloud-enabled business model today, leadership has been renamed as digital leadership. The various applications and benefits of cloud computing can be achieved by businesses that have restructured their business models and integrated various cloud-based applications (Jiang et al., 2013). The cloud-based applications especially become effective because they help reduce the complexity of the IT infrastructure. Businesses are also able to manage their resources from various locations effectively. The integration of cloud resources has been found to effectively ensure that the businesses' success in digital transformation has been promoted.

New age Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) strategy prioritizes the challenges organizations face implementing the cloud(Dash, 2020b). Digital transformation remains a challenge for most businesses. The success rate for businesses transforming into digital models is below 50%. Many businesses cannot effectively implement technologies that promote their digital transformation success. Cloud services have, however, been identified as a significant solution for businesses trying to transform into a digital model (Liu et al., 2017). The development of the internet and its

popularity have contributed to how well businesses benefit from cloud-based services. The report below tries to identify some of the ways that cloud resources promote digital transformation success. The effective use of cloud resources is critical to success in digital transformation.

Research Question: How does the effective use of cloud resources promote an organization's digital transformation success?

Objectives

- To identify some of the critical cloud resources for businesses today.
- To describe how these cloud resources promote and influence digital transformation.
- To recommend how business leaders could effectively use cloud resources as a secret tool in their digital transformation success.

Literature Review

Cloud computing is one of the revolutionary technologies today. The technology has a vast list of applications that promote efficiency within businesses. Identifying how to use these technologies effectively is an effective approach to obtaining the most benefits (Almorsy et al., 2011). The cloud resources comprise the various services offered by cloud computing providers. Cloud resources are virtual machines that customers rent for specific computational needs and storage capacity increments (Omar, 2015). The providers can charge specific amounts for the cloud instances, which allow users to access their resources.

Cloud resources have become increasingly popular due to the applications they offer to their users (Almorsy et al., 2011). The resources are critical in saving costs for companies. The cost for high-end computers that can effectively compute some of the services business needs. Obtaining such computers for every employee in an organization is increasingly costly (Omar, 2015). The computation can be conducted on the cloud through the necessary cloud resources. Storage cloud resources also promote data backup, therefore assisting in disaster recovery. Figure 1 below identifies some of the applications of cloud computing. The cloud resources identified are significantly popular and help businesses across various industries (Jiang et al., 2013).

Figure 1: Examples of Cloud Resources

Digital transformation is how businesses convert all their business operations to be achieved through digital technologies (Matt et al., 2015). The integration of digital technologies across all business operations helps a business in promoting its digital transformation success. However, Matt et al. (2015) identify that the digital transformation process is significantly challenging. Most businesses fail in their digital transformation process. Most business leaders cannot effectively digitally transform their organizations due to these challenges. Identifying these challenges is crucial in promoting digital transformation success.

There exists a gap in identifying how the effective use of cloud resources can help promote digital transformation success. Jiang et al. (2013) indicate that cloud resources are becoming increasingly popular, with more providers promoting their resources. Business leaders, however, lack the knowledge of how they can effectively use these resources for their digital transformation process. The current research should research and promote knowledge for business leaders. Integrating cloud resources will then promote how businesses can succeed in digital transformation.

Methodology

Theoretical Framework

The study is guided by the Technology Acceptance Model framework. The model identifies that the perceived ease of use and usefulness of a technology system will influence the individual's intention to use it. The model, therefore, identifies the usefulness and ease of use associated with cloud resources (Oh & Yoon, 2014). The acceptance of cloud resources significantly influences the digital transformation success. The model, therefore, guides the theory that accepting cloud resource applications significantly influences the success of digital transformation (Oh & Yoon, 2014). Figure 2 below identifies the TAM model for cloud resources and how the acceptance impacts the digital transformation success. The mode acts as a reliable tool in guiding the research and analysis process. Identifying the external factors that influence the usefulness and ease of use associated with cloud resources will showcase what services are more effective in promoting digital transformation in businesses.

Figure 2: TAM Model

Data Collection

The research adopted a critical review approach. The study includes the collection of secondary research studies from well-respected journals. The critical review engages a review of the collected data and an analysis of the results identified (Page, 2011). There are many reputable journals with significant databases where the secondary research will be obtained (Page, 2011). The inclusion criteria focus on studies that describe how to effectively benefit from using cloud resources. The studies that describe challenges in digital transformation will also be identified, showcasing key issues facing businesses today. Each paper selected was screened for quality. Quality journals are necessary to promote the validity of the research study. The papers were then reviewed, and their findings were analyzed below.

Data Analysis

The studies included different findings, which were reviewed to answer the objectives identified above. Each objective is showcased below, showcasing how the effective use of cloud resources can help promote success in digital transformation. The themes across the studies were obtained to help with the discussion showcased below.

Results and Discussion

The research question is answered strategically based on the three research objectives mentioned above.

Critical Business Cloud Resources Used by Businesses Today

There is a vast list of cloud resources used every day by businesses. Many companies are today benefitting from using storage resources from cloud computing platforms (Borkowski et al., 2016). Companies are today producing vast amounts of data every day (Alhamazani et al., 2014). The need for extra storage has pushed more businesses towards using cloud computing platforms to obtain extra storage. Therefore, storage is one of the critical cloud resources businesses can use for their development (Alhamazani et al., 2014). The storage allows businesses to access their resources from any location with internet connectivity.

The next critical cloud resource is the servers. Servers in the cloud are critical because they allow companies to host their projects and websites (Zhan et al., 2015). Companies that have an e-commerce platform are today able to benefit from servers in the cloud effectively. The service ensures that a business can operate more effectively without the necessary challenges of acquiring a server for its e-commerce business platform (Dash & Swayamsiddha, 2020; Zhan et al., 2015).

Applications are a significant resource that businesses benefit from the cloud. Businesses are today able to request computation of various services from their servers. The application describes an effective tool through which businesses can thrive. The application remains critical to the way a business can thrive. Businesses can request specific resources that help in completing their tasks. The introduction of cloud computing reduces the need for acquiring specific machines or software resources that can achieve this type of application. This significantly promotes the impact associated with this cloud resource.

How These Cloud Resources Promote And Influence Digital Transformation

The digital transformation process is challenging for businesses today. A few companies succeed in their digital transformation strategies (Schwertner, 2017). The cloud resources identified above, however, showcase that they significantly influence the digitization of services within a business.

Figure 3 below identifies some of the challenges associated with the digital transformation process. Each concern should be addressed for companies to succeed in digital transformation.

Figure 3: Digital Transformational Challenges

The cost involved in digital transformation is a major concern for most businesses. Figure 3 above shows that budget constraints are a major challenge associated with digital transformation in businesses (Majchrzak et al., 2016). Investing in technologies to promote efficiency within a business' operations is expensive. Cloud resources introduce a cheaper and more effective solution in such situations. Businesses can invest significantly less in the digital transformation (Schwertner, 2017). Paying subscription fees for these resources is cheaper than acquiring the technologies themselves.

Security concerns remain one of the main factors that limit the ability of businesses to succeed in their digital transformation strategies (Sharma & Dash, 2020; Kane, 2018). Cloud resources have become an effective tool for businesses to promote their security. Most cloud computing service providers have high-end encryption technologies that ensure information has been protected (Majchrzak et al., 2016). The database cloud resource can, therefore, be used by organizations to improve their security (Borkowski et al., 2016). Companies can then be assured that the digital transformation process cannot be impacted by data theft or intellectual property within the company.

Digital transformation increases the amount of data that a company produces every day. Most companies become overwhelmed with the data they manage (Riasanow et al., 2017). Cloud resources, however, introduce a significant solution for businesses with increased amounts of information. Digital transformation is better managed by ensuring that the data is stored in the storage resources in the cloud. Storing the data and information in the cloud allows businesses to complete their operations more efficiently. This also shows a significant method through which cloud resources can be used effectively in influencing digital transformation (Dash & Swayamsiddha, 2020).

The risk-averse culture, organizational management concerns, and internal change resistance are all addressed effectively through the applications cloud resources introduce to a business (Kane, 2018). The management can effectively use cloud resources such as data analytics applications and make more efficient decisions for the organization. The employees can also reduce their workload by applying cloud resources such as project management tools (Riasanow et al., 2017).

The employees will also enjoy more convenience through the cloud resources employed. The convenience of working from home will be introduced through the ability to access company resources from any location. Each of these factors will significantly promote the digital transformation success that a business achieves.

Lack of expertise is another major digital transformation challenge (Sharma, 2017a). Most businesses fail in their digital transformation because they lack the needed expertise (Reddy & Reinartz, 2017). Cloud resources are, however, an effective approach that businesses could use when acquiring experts to help with some of their business operations (Kane, 2018). The benefits identified above show how cloud resources can help promote success in digital transformation within a business.

Recommendations to Business Leaders.

Business leaders should identify challenges that influence their digital transformation strategy to promote its success. After identifying the key challenges impacting the digital transformation strategy, the business leaders can implement some of the cloud resources identified above to address the concerns (Sharma, 2017b). Cloud resources are identified to be critical solutions for most of the challenges businesses experience (Borkowski et al., 2016). Business leaders should, therefore, identify their challenges and then proceed to identify which cloud resources can help address these challenges more effectively.

Business leaders must also align their digital transformational strategy towards some of the business outcomes within the organization (Reddy & Reinartz, 2017). The resistance to change from the employees is a serious challenge that could impact the overall success the business achieves. The solution can best be addressed by aligning the digital transformational strategies with business outcomes. This solution is also crucial to promoting how well the business can succeed in digital transformation.

Conclusion

The effective use of cloud resources in digital transformation is crucial to promoting the success of the transformation process. Digital transformation promotes productivity and efficiency within a business. Successful digital transformation also helps a business to become more competitive within its industry. The challenges that impact the digital transformation success are significant for the business's success. Security, resistance to change, and cost are some identified challenges. These challenges can effectively be addressed through the implementation and effective use of cloud resources. The TAM model identifies that the usefulness and ease of use attributed to the cloud resources promote their overall application across organizations. The increased usage, in turn, promotes digital transformation success by addressing the challenges impacting the business.

The main limitation identified within the research study is that it only focuses on business leaders as the only stakeholders involved in the digital transformation process. The digital transformation process engages many stakeholders within the business. Therefore, the impact and influence attributed to these stakeholders are a limitation. Future research studies should identify other stakeholders and their impact on the success of the digital transformation process. The studies can then identify critical actions that each of these stakeholders could implement to promote the success of the digital transformation strategy.

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